

The cover features a night sky with the Milky Way galaxy visible, set against a landscape of rolling hills and a rocky foreground. The text is overlaid on the upper portion of the image.

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ЭТИМОЛОГИЯ ТОПОНИМА “SURKHANDARYA”

Аннотация: В этой статье обсуждаются вопросы, связанные с этимологией термина Сурхандарья. Он посвящен идеям ученых, которые провели тщательные исследования в этой области, особенно с этим понятием. Также учитываются отношения между народами в Центральной Азии на протяжении веков, чтобы определить происхождение термина Сурхандарья.

Ключевые слова: топонимы, этимология, гидроним, Сурхандарья, турецкие языки.

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THE ETYMOLOGY OF THE TOPONYM “SURKHANDARYA”

Annotation: This article discusses the issues related to the etymology of the term Surkhandarya. It deals with the ideas of the scientists who made a thorough research in this field, especially with this notion. The relationships between nations in the Central Asia over the centuries are also taken into account in order to define the origin of the term Surkhandarya.

Keywords: toponyms, etymology, gydronym, Surkhandarya, Turkish languages.

Toponym is a branch of linguistics which only deals with investigating the names of places in detail. Mainly, it consists of two objects: microtoponym and macrotoponym. Microtoponym explains the etymology of the names of small places. Macrotoponym investigates the origin of the names of big places.

The most peculiar features of toponyms are that they depend on subjects like history, geography and archeology. Scientists use the way of asking from local residents, while gathering information about toponyms and researching the names of places [7; 38].

Apart from this, toponyms have another branch like antrotoponym which explains the origin of the names and nicknames of people and ethnotoponym which explain the historical etymology of the names of nations, tribes and ethnic groups that have become the names of places.

The history of homeland, its sacred name is always appealing for every person living there. Thus, our nation is proud of their cultural and spiritual wealth which has

been hereditary from our ancestors. From ancient times people used to give special names for every event and places. Consequently, this tradition is still in use. For this striking custom, these kinds of names have been coming from generation to generation. Surely, they gave those names according to the natural condition, local people's life-style and vocation. These terms reflect the glory past, rich culture and spirituality of the nation.

It is obvious that a nation has never come into formation in one territory without being in contact with other nations. During historical evolution, different nations made cultural and economic relationship with each other. As a consequence of cultural approaches, they began living in one territory despite speaking in different languages and they found special names for their destinations according to both nations' tradition.

It is known that Surkhandarya is the name of region which is located in the south of Uzbekistan. In fact, it is the name of river which joins the Amu-darya River. In this article the etymology of the conception of "Surkhandarya" is widely discussed. Scientists claim that the hydronym "Surkhandarya" is divided into two parts: "Surkhan" and "darya".

S.Korayev showed two explanations of the hydronym "Surkhan" to prove his proposal: 1) "Surkhan" is a changed form of "Surkhab" [3; 115] that meant "red water" During centuries, "Surkhab" was changed into "surkhan". 2) The next explanation is that "Surkh" is a name of the Turkmen tribes. According to E.M.Mirzayev, he claims the concept "Surkh" is a persian word "" (surh) and it means "red", "reddish" [1; p.253]. T.Nafasov also strongly believes that "Surkhan" means "red water" ("surkh" — red, "an">"ab" — water) in Tajik language [5; 170]. In reality, the river becomes dreggy and reddish in spring and summer months and only becomes clear in autumn and winter [5; 170]. So, it can be concluded that the first word the conception of "Surkhan" means "red water".

As for the second word, ancient people combined the word "darya" to "Surkhan". According to a number of scientists' view, the word "darya" belongs to Iranian language. However, I.A.Ismoilov considers that "darya" is widely spread along the whole Central Asia and it is being used for hydronyms [6; 53]. This can prove that the word "darya"

does not belong to Iranian languages. In Turkish languages “darya” is widely used and it means “river” and “river watercourse”.

Furthermore, SH. S.Kamoliddinov points out that the word “darya” has the form as a “dare” and “dere” in Hagus language [2; 30]. However, the history of The Hagus nation has been distant from the history of Iranian peoples and any Iranian word cannot be found in Hagus language. So it can be concluded that the etymology of “darya” fully belongs to Turkish language and as it is stated above, it means “river” in the language.

In conclusion, through learning the etymology of “Surkhandarya”, we can understand how the conception was originated, why the words were chosen, what the word means and from what language they were taken. Moreover, we can also acknowledge that the toponym reflects the glory past, wealthy culture and magnificent traditions of Uzbek and Tajik in its essence.

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